

PROCESS MANAGEMENT IN AN ORGANIZATION IN THE AEROSPACE INDUSTRY IN TERMS OF THEIR VERTICAL INTEGRATION

Author(s)*: Gheorghe Ioan POP ¹, Aurel Mihail ȚÎȚU ^{2,3}
Position: PhD Student ¹, Professor ^{2,3}
University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest
Splaiul Independenței 313, București 060042¹
Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu
Victoriei Street no. 10, code 550024, Sibiu, România ²
The Academy of Romanian Scientists
54, Splaiul Independenței, Sector 5, Bucharest, Romania ³
Email: popghitza@gmail.com ¹, mihail.titu@ulbsibiu.ro ^{2,3}

Abstract

Purpose – The scientific paper focuses on a pragmatic study regarding the existing processes in an organization and how to integrate them into an efficient quality management system.

Methodology/approach - A process map was conceived in its own vision, analyzed and subsequently argued in an organization with a field of activity in the aerospace industry. The subject of manufacturing processes in such an organization has been reported to process and inspection standards.

Findings – Operational processes, namely process improvement, are a key priority in the business environment. Support processes contribute to supporting business processes through methods, techniques and software applications in order to design, adopt, control and analyze operational processes that primarily involve people, organizations, applications, documents and other sources of information. The importance of establishing a process map in the management area and then the manufacturing one in an organization in the aerospace industry is an extremely important step in solving problems and implicitly non-conformities.

Research limitations/implications – A properly prepared process map can certainly lead to efficiency and effectiveness. This aspect can lead to favorable results related to the quality management of the processes, there being a correct functionality of all the management activities as well as of the technical ones.

Practical implications – The scientific paper presents a serious documentation regarding the possibilities of operationalization of the operational processes and the support processes in an organization in the aerospace field in order to manufacture some structural components.

Originality/value – The contributions we promote are of a conceptual, applied and technical nature. At the same time, the management is not neglected at all, so that an important and essential contribution is the way in which the authors impose their point of view on the concrete way in the organizational management at company level.

Key words: process map, aerospace industry, process management.

Introduction

Within an industrial organization, operational processes are those production processes with the role of making products. As for the production processes, they represent the activities carried out with the help of natural equipment and processes, organized and led by people in an organized way in order to obtain some products.

From a systemic point of view, the objectives of the production process involve the transformation of inputs (materials, labor, energy, etc.) into outputs in the form of semi-finished products, finished products or services.

For years, process improvement has been a major business priority. Companies have been using a value-based management approach since the 1990s in a constant effort to increase its value. The principles of value-based business process management have been introduced in business process management. Existing analyzes of this problem operate at a high level (i.e., corporate), preventing the use of value-based business process management at the operational process level, both in research and in practice. Authors such as (Buhl, Roglinger, Stockl, and Braunwarth, 2015), (Bolsinger, 2015), (Rotaru, Wilkin, Churilov, Neiger, and Ceglowski, 2011), have approached this issue through the prism of an evaluation that brings business process management. based on value at the operational process level, showing how the estimated net present value adjusted for the risk of a process can be determined. The evaluation calculations performed in these researches provide information about the theoretical foundations of the processes and help to improve the computing capabilities of some existing process modeling tools.

In any company there are main processes, management processes and support processes. Specifically, for example:

- the main processes relate to production and services provided;
- the management processes aim at establishing the company's policies and objectives, the analysis performed by the management, analyzes and decisions regarding the resources and
- support processes take into account human resources, infrastructure, work environment, supply, transport, logistics, internal audit, improvement, etc.

Supporting business processes through methods, techniques and software applications is done in order to design, adopt, control and analyze operational processes involving people, organizations, applications, documents and other sources of information (Weske, van der Aalst, and Verbeek, 2004).

Map of management processes in an industrial organization

Process maps are adopted by organizations as the foundation of business process management initiatives. They play an important role in providing an overview of all processes, so that the basic operation of a company can be understood without necessarily going into details, which are usually presented in the single model of the management process (Malinova and Mendling, The Effect Of Process Map Design Quality On Process Management Success, 2013)

Instead, the process map focuses on the representation of classifications, relationships, and dependencies between single processes. These aspects are usually illustrated as a visual representation, serving as a basic means of communication and for a better understanding of business processes (Kesari and Chang, 2003). Based on the process map design, the next steps of the business management process life cycle could follow successively (Dumas, La Rosa, Mendling, and Reijers, 2013). Given this, the quality of the process map is essential for the success of process management. Numerous research efforts have been made regarding the design and redesign of process models (Kock, 2006). Recently, new navigation techniques through large collections of process models have been the focus of research (Radulescu, 2006).

One way to handle a large number of models is by using a process architecture. A process architecture is a collection of process models organized systematically within an organization (Malinova, Leopold, and Mendling, An Empirical Investigation on the Design of Process Architectures, 2003)

Usually, a process map is the input to the different levels of a process architecture, where the detailed modeling of the process takes place. Different approaches to process architecture design have been defined (Dijkman, Vanderfeesten, and Reijers, 2011), (Malinova, Leopold, and Mendling, An Empirical Investigation on the Design of Process Architectures, 2003). Also, the importance of process architecture for the success of business management processes was highlighted (Sedera, Gable, Rosemann, and Smyth, 2004), (Bandara, Gable, and Rosemann, 2005), (Rosemann, 2006). Regardless of its obvious importance, the design of the process map was hardly subject to research. Practitioners seem to approach this challenge rather as an art based on their own creativity and a broadly defined set of concepts in designing a process map. As a result, a variety of process map models are used in practice, despite the fact that most aim for the same goal. Many of them are obvious cases of mastery,

where the concepts used for their design are not based on generally accepted engineering principles for the design of visual notations (Moody, 2009).

Given this diversity, there is a strong demand for research into the concepts used and represented in a process map (Recker, Rosemann, Green, and Indulska, 2011).

The importance of mapping management and manufacturing processes in an industrial organization

W. Edwards Deming stated that "If you can't describe what you're doing as a process, you don't know what you're doing."

Any organization can improve its quality management system. The conformity of the processes, products and quality management system in the organization can be demonstrated, even if the standard does not explicitly require it, by preparing documents, such as (Mendes, 2013): process map (matrix); product specifications; production programs; list of approved suppliers; test and inspection plans; installation, operation and service manuals; rules and procedures.

Figure 1. Documents to demonstrate compliance

The process map is a graphical representation of all the processes identified within the organization. This map illustrates the process flows that influence quality. A map (matrix) of a process represents the process as a whole, from beginning to end (www.ro.wikipedia.org, 2020), (Gotz, 2012). Figure 2 shows the components of the process map.

Any quality management system process can be divided into sub-processes that are clearly defined in a quality management system process matrix. The requirements are set out in documents called specifications. They are unique to the process, product or organization, and for this reason are not detailed in the quality standard (www.improvement-skills.co.uk, 2020).

In making the process map, the same importance is given to the performance of all component processes. This performance is established on the basis of the specific objectives for each process or through performance indicators.

Figure 2. Process map components

The usefulness of a correctly made process map is felt when there are changes in the organization or when it is intended to explain the principle of operation of the company. According to Figure 3 on the process map can be indicated: system procedures (PS); operational procedures (OP); quality plans (PC); work instructions (I); technologies (T); standards (S); contracts (outsourcing processes); formulation; any other documents that are used in defining and carrying out the processes.

Procedures are documents that show how the activities are carried out, so that anyone can work without mistakes, even if there is no maximum number of procedures, for the implementation of a quality management system according to ISO 9001, 6 system procedures are absolutely necessary, and all other procedures are operational.

An organization can write a number of procedures equal to the number of processes within it. However, the possibility of performing only one procedure related to several processes of the same type, or the reverse situation in which a single process can be described in several documents is not excluded.

The 6 mandatory procedures specified in ISO 9001 are with reference to processes, more precisely to:

- how documents in the organization are kept under control;
- how the organization's records are kept under control;
- how the product found to be non-compliant is kept under control;
- how to perform the internal audit;
- how corrective actions are controlled;
- the way in which preventive actions are controlled.

It is recommended that the names of the procedures be associated with the chapters in the ISO 9001 standard that refer to the analyzed process.

Figure 3. Aspects indicated in the process map

Figure 4. Mandatory procedures according to ISO 9001

The processes and their integration in the quality management system in an organization in the aeronautical field

Figure 5 shows how certification organizations structure the requirements of the quality management system in the aeronautical industry.

Figure 5. The main processes of the Quality management system

Industrial organizations in the aeronautical field must be AS 9100 certified, so they must have a quality management system implemented according to its requirements.

Management, support and operational processes are included in the requirements of the AS 9100 standard to the same extent as in ISO 9001.

The integration of management processes, Figure 5, from the perspective of the standard, is approached by integrating leadership requirements in all processes and equally by controlling management decisions, by thinking based on probable risk.

Also, the approach of all processes through a continuous improvement, makes the management processes to be integrated in all processes and under the system processes.

Figure 6 represents the distribution and connections of processes in an industrial organization in the aeronautical field, specifically on the manufacture of metal structural components.

The processes are distributed according to the purpose they have within the organization. Thus we can identify:

- Management processes;
- Operational processes;
- Support processes.

As can be seen in Figure 6, customer requirements are the main entry into the organizational system. These requirements are transformed by the organization, through the prism of the organizational context. Outputs, resulting products, verified by the customer, in addition to financial benefits, are also measured by the degree of customer satisfaction that have a direct impact on the evaluation of the organization's performance and also on the process of continuous improvement.

Figure 6. Process map in an industrial organization in the aeronautical industry

The leadership process (position 5 Figure 6) is a management process with a major impact in the organization, which is why these organizations emphasize the commitment of senior management and their level of involvement in processes. The activity of the management process is carried out in relation to the context of the organization.

The ways in which this commitment is met are:

- Assuming responsibility for the effectiveness of the quality management system;
- Involvement in the development of quality objectives so that they are correlated with the context of the organization;
- Involvement in the process of integrating the requirements of the quality management system in the processes of the organization;
- Allocation of the necessary resources for maintaining the quality management system;
- Promoting continuous improvement;
- Supporting other relevant management positions to demonstrate their leadership, as applicable to their area of responsibility;

The management commitment and its principles are formalized within the quality management system by defining the quality policy of the organization.

The aeronautical quality policy contains generally applicable directives, such as:

- Compliance with laws and regulations specific to the aeronautical field applicable to the activity sector;
- Clear definition of the objectives and targets of the quality level in all hierarchical structures within the organization and their periodic analysis;
- Decision making using objective data;
- Promoting thinking based on risk analysis;
- Promoting and developing a culture of aviation safety;
- Active monitoring of the process of improving the quality management system.

Management activities, in addition to making a commitment and defining the context of the organization and its objectives, have the role of defining the organizational structure of the organization. Thus, the definition of roles, responsibilities and authority closes the functions of this process of management, leadership. Role allocation is based on the processes of organizations and their interaction.

Achieving the objectives generated by the strategic plan of any company is the goal of the entire management, and the way it is done is planning (position 6 Figure 6).

Planning is the key to the success of any organization regardless of the field of activity. Thus, the planning of the organization's objectives will be found at all hierarchical levels. Planning can be accomplished by carrying out development projects, long-term or short-term production projects or improvement projects.

Also, planning to achieve quality goals requires a well-established plan, integrated into all processes within the organization. Also, each process must be identified with a quality target correlated with that of the organization.

The coordination of the planned activities is achieved by analyzing the impact and influence of each process in the entire organizational system, in other words, by organization.

It is considered that the level and quality of the influence and impact analysis has a major effect in the allocation and management of resources.

The control process by measuring and evaluating the activities within the organization is represented by the processes in box 9 and 10 (Figure 6). Thus, the process of evaluating the performance of the organization is performed through management analysis and audits of all processes.

In addition, the improvement process helps to evaluate the activities and at the same time becomes a major input in the improvement planning process. The process of analyzing the non-conformities of the product, technological process and system, represent important inputs in the evaluation process, also used as input in the realization of improvement plans.

Customer satisfaction is used by organizations as a marketing tool. The level of customer satisfaction indirectly determines the quality of the products.

Customer satisfaction has a major impact in the improvement process, being considered a factor with high influence in the improvement processes.

Support processes (heading 7 Figure 6) are the processes that deal mainly with human resources management, in particular:

- The process of hiring human resources;
- Competence assessment process;
- The process of awareness of human resources at all hierarchical levels;
- The communication process inside and outside the organization.

The quality of the output of this process - especially the quality of human resources knowledge - has an impact on the entire organization. This knowledge plays a special role in management processes, and also in processes based on human resources knowledge.

Operational Processes (position 8 Figure 6) are the "engine" of the organization. Thus, the processes within this group of processes are very important and they are given special attention.

Under the operational planning and control process is that process that develops and monitors operational plans including all others under operational processes.

The process of managing requirements and services is the process of entering the operational plan. This process has as input the requirements of the products directly from the customer. It is considered that the level and manner of interpretation of the requirements may lead to the success of the operational plan or its failure. This process is considered a critical process, due to the impact it can have on the organization, both on other processes and on products. In other words, incorrect or incomplete interpretation of product requirements may result in the production of non-compliant products.

Within the operational processes it is also found under the process of design and development of products and services, which also has a major impact on the fulfillment of the operational plan.

Conclusions

The structure of the quality management system in industrial organizations in the aeronautical field is based on the AS 9100 standard. However, the challenge for companies is to comply with the requirements of this standard and the requirements of customers at the same time in product manufacturing processes.

The complexity of product requirements in the field of aeronautics requires management processes an approach based on risk analysis. Thus, management decisions are influenced both by the knowledge of managers in the field in which they operate, and by the available information of related processes, which they can use.

In an industrial manufacturing organization, the interaction between the processes of the management system is achieved through human resources, coordinated by process managers (Figure 7).

Each process manager must know very well the processes of the entire quality management system, so as to align the process he coordinates with the requirements of the system and equally necessary to know everything under the processes, activities, inputs and outputs of the process. which he coordinates. In order for the system to work, process managers must also know the processes they intersect with, according to the quality management system, but the large volume of information and

knowledge specific to each process makes the management activity considerably more difficult. Sorting and analyzing all this information consume a long time, which is not available in management decisions.

Figure 7. The interaction of processes within a system

The industrial organization operates using the knowledge of human resources and the capacity and capability of the equipment.

The organization achieves its functional role, the target of quality and financial level, only because management decisions and processes are managed in relation to the strategic vision.

The analysis of the efficiency of each process is related to the other processes, regardless of its complexity. Thus, it is necessary to develop a model for analyzing the efficiency of the processes, in relation to the own resources of the process and to the interactions of the other processes.

Analyzing the processes of the organization's system in terms of interactions and the impact on product quality, the process of preparing the launch documentation in manufacturing was chosen for conducting the study.

In manufacturing, and not only, the efficiency of each process is influenced by management functions and the volume and quality of human resources knowledge. At the same time, the multitude of parameters that can influence the process, makes the management activity to be seen as a function controlled by all parameters simultaneously.

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